

**Delivering the next generation of open
Integrated Assessment MOdels for
Net-zero, sustainable Development**

D7.3 – The DIAMOND Project CDE Plan – Update 1

WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate & Exploit

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable serves primarily as a reference document among consortium partners to support the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the project. It can also be used by other similar projects to draw from our planning (ambition) and implementation (experiences) so that they can in turn develop a robust CDE strategy.

3. Short summary of results

This report is the first update to the DIAMOND project's strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities to relevant audiences.

As in the initial CDE plan described in deliverable D7.2, the report first defines the scope of CDE in the context of DIAMOND and sets the overall targets of the project, which aims to follow a tailored approach to develop inclusive messages and convey them to specific audiences through efficient communication means. The report also sets quantifiable indicators for specific activities that will be tracked throughout the duration of the project, such as publishing at least 10 articles and press releases throughout the project.

Next, the report identifies the project's target audiences, which include modellers, researchers, policymakers, and industries, as well as NGOs and civil society organisations. A multi-pronged selection of promotional channels/platforms is suggested, to more effectively target these varied populations. The promotional channels to reach project audiences include the project's website, social media (e.g., X, LinkedIn, and Instagram), the I²AM PARIS platform, synergies with other relevant projects, open-access papers, and more. A visual identity and a logo for the project have been developed and have been used throughout the project, including in the design of the project website and promotional materials such as infographics and presentations.

The plan concludes by reporting progress towards the CDE indicators, as of May 2024, and outlining next steps for improving dissemination. The CDE plan will be further updated in September 2025 (Month 34 of the project).

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA'COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
ETH	EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH	CH	
UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report provides an update to the initial strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of the DIAMOND project that was published in deliverable D7.2 in May 2023. As in the initial report, this first update begins by defining the scope of communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of DIAMOND and by setting the CDE targets of the project. Additionally, the report sets quantifiable indicators for specific activities that will be monitored throughout the duration of the project, such as achieving 10 articles and press releases in the project's course.

Next, the report identifies the target audiences of the project as well as the promotional channels to reach them. The project audiences range from scientists/researchers/academia to decision-makers in policy/industry/NGOs, and civil society and will be further refined during the project. In order to reach these different audiences, a diverse selection of promotional channels is suggested. Central to the communication process is the DIAMOND website, which will enable users to learn about the project and find links to all other promotional material. Similarly, processes related to the continuous enhancement of the I²AM PARIS platform to facilitate data harmonisation and modelling and foster the co-creation of assumptions, parameters, and scenarios, as well as host material related to the newly developed models are briefly outlined. External communication channels are also envisioned to play an instrumental role in the project's CDE, including social media (e.g., X, LinkedIn, and Instagram), news websites and blogs (e.g., EURACTIV and The Conversation), events such as conferences and workshops, and synergies with other relevant projects.

The CDE plan also outlines the types of materials envisioned to promote the DIAMOND scope, objectives, and results through the identified channels. The visual identity and logo of the project have already been developed, based on the project's main messages of enhancing modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways. This visual identity is used in the design of the project website and promotional materials including articles, infographics, videos, and presentations. Furthermore, project updates are distributed via the project's bi-monthly newsletters and partners' newsletters as well, which will further increase the project's visibility.

The plan concludes by listing implemented promotional activities in the first 18 months of the project, such as the establishment of social media channels (X, LinkedIn, Instagram), the promotion of the project scope and activities through them, and the participation to various events and conferences. The CDE plan will be further updated in September 2025 (Month 34 of the project) to report progress towards the project's CDE goals, assess the implemented use of the promotional channels and means, and modify the CDE strategy as needed.

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1 Introduction

DIAMOND seeks to update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It further enhances modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies.

This is done through the integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project develops a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establishes vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

DIAMOND aims to:

- produce iteratively updated, upgraded, open-source versions of six leading IAMs;
- further enhance the capabilities of IAMs to assess the trade-offs and co-benefits of a transition to climate neutrality with other SDGs;
- enable the systematic evaluation of interactions among climate change mitigation, adaptation, risks, physical impacts;
- validate the capacity of the enhanced IAMs to support climate and other development policies and COVID-19 recovery efforts at multi-level aspects;
- transparently open all modelling enhancements to the wider modelling community;
- develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions, legitimise the implementation process and model development, and optimise the communication of project results.

This report describes a first update to the initial strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of information and results of DIAMOND to relevant audiences. Overall, the CDE plan has the following objectives:

1. communicating project results and successful practices to demonstrate the project's impact to a wider audience, both online and in-person;
2. creating the means to disseminate results to stakeholders, including policymakers, NGOs, industries, the scientific community, and even citizens, motivating them to exploit DIAMOND results;
3. promoting the exploitation potential of the results for the six IAMs, both during and beyond the project life, through partners' networks and ongoing activities.

These objectives, along with other special requirements for DIAMOND, are described in detail in Chapter 2. In order to fulfill these objectives, the CDE plan also discusses the target audiences and their characteristics and outlines communication channels to share project results so that they are openly available and easily accessible to everyone. Additionally, the plan describes a list of methods tailored to each target group, such as communication materials, a visual identity, and social media packs for the general public as well as external conferences and synergies and collaborations with other EU projects for academic dissemination.

In summary, the CDE plan is structured based on the following questions on the promotion process:

- **To whom?** Identification of the audiences to which the project will be promoted (Chapter 3).
- **How?** Analysis of potential promotional channels and selection of the most appropriate ones, according

to the target audience and the message to be disseminated (Chapter 4).

- **What?** Planning and implementation of the CDE activities (Chapter 5 for activities that are already implemented and Chapter 6 for next steps on improving dissemination).

2 Goals and targets of the CDE plan

2.1 The three pillars of promotion: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the wider public, regarding the project and its results. Apart from establishing the branding of DIAMOND as a project about improving IAMs, communication efforts focuses on promoting pertinent results and novel insights generated by the improved models, showcasing applications to EU policy benchmarks, national energy and climate plans, and strategies for businesses, energy-intensive industries, and financial institutions.

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well on how the outcomes can be exploited by interested parties. The main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who could use the results in their operation. In the case of DIAMOND, these are 1) modellers working on IAMs and scenario analysis who could adopt the project's open-source improvements in their own models, 2) researchers working on climate change mitigation who could update their work through the project's outcomes, 3) policymakers at different levels (EU, national, and local policymakers), 4) industries which could exploit results to take more robust decisions in issues related to mitigation and adaptation, considering important but previously unexploited issues, 5) NGOs, civil society organisations and citizens, in general, who would be provided with insights on how small scale actions and lifestyle and behavioural changes could contribute to enhancing climate targets and what the benefits and burdens of these actions entail.

Exploitation is the effective practical use of project results through scientific, economic, political, or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audiences of exploitation are the same as the ones suitable for dissemination.

2.2 Overall Targets

Creating a living document

The CDE plan will be periodically updated throughout the project while we will also monitor all CDE activities. All CDE activities up to May 2024 are documented in this report, which will be further revised in September 2025 (Month 34). The WP7 team will make the required adjustments to the project's actions if there is a risk that the desired outcomes might not be met. The plan will be also continuously updated with feedback from stakeholders, following the overall CODESIGN methodology of the project (see WP2). This two-way communication will be especially prominent in the development and operation of the website and the new functionalities of the I²AM PARIS platform.

Customising information to target audiences

The CDE strategy is taking into account a customised approach to successfully communicate the project's key messages to its various target groups based on the audience segmentation that is initially selected (see Chapter 3). Accordingly, the WP7 team is creating distinct core messages for each group and link them with appropriate communication channels. Each target audience has formal and informal channels for communication (e.g., scientific publications versus scientific groups in X and LinkedIn). Therefore, in addition to being mindful of the language used, it is important to consider communication style and tone. While the essential scientific content will

stay unchanged, communication initiatives will be adapted for various stakeholder groups. Nevertheless, for the sake of scientific relevance and integrity, the project findings will not be downplayed, even when conflicting with particular interests.

Adopting an inclusive and gender-sensitive approach

Gender is a focal point in DIAMOND as it is central in the formation, response, and responsibility bearing of the energy transition (e.g., see Fathallah & Pyakurel, 2020). Gender will be prominent in the CODESIGN (WP2) block of the project, both in terms of a continuous discussion theme among stakeholders in the contexts of where, when, and how gender issues should be represented in scenarios and models, but also by achieving a balanced gender representation in all knowledge co-production activities. Similarly, the WP7 team will ensure a good balance of stakeholders of different genders, ages, and backgrounds in its dissemination activities.

Planning for a restriction-resilient CDE

Due to uncertainties related to major global disturbances such as a eventual resurgence of COVID-19, appropriate methodological alternatives have been identified to ensure that the dissemination and communication activities are not brought to a complete standstill and DIAMOND can continue producing results. While online meetings and communication have become common during the last years, for the sake of building trust with the project team and with external stakeholders, physical events will still be used when possible. In cooperation with the project coordinator, the WP7 team will constantly monitor major global disturbances and decide when each methodological alternative will be used. Table 1 shows activities that are identified as potentially vulnerable to such disturbances, along with their methodological alternatives.

Table 1. DIAMOND activities that can be potentially affected by travelling restrictions

Activity	Preferred implementation	Methodological alternatives
Co-design activities	In-person workshops	Virtual workshops, carefully designed to reduce video-call fatigue and secure time for discussion and input from all participants
Annual project meetings among consortium partners	In-person meetings	Online meetings through MS Teams
Conferences, pitch meetings with policymakers, and other communication and dissemination activities	In-person and online activities	Only online (through MS Teams)
Final EU conference	In-person and online event	Only online, as a webinar (through MS Teams)

Going open access and paper-free

All content will be provided in open-access format. Regarding scientific publications, we will prioritise not only high-impact but also fully open-access journals offering, when feasible, open peer review, such as Open Research Europe which will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold

open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated Zenodo community¹, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability.

The CDE strategy is designed to be as paper-free content as possible, having at least an 80% digital communication and dissemination focus. Printed material will be used sparingly and only when deemed necessary to the CDE activity at hand. However, templates for printed material are provided on the website, allowing any interested party to download and use them.

2.3 Monitored CDE activities and indicators

To ensure that project results are successfully communicated, disseminated, and exploited, a set of targets and indicators has been set (Table 2). Progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis, to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or to take corrective measures if necessary (see Chapter 5 for the current progress). The communication channels and materials to achieve these targets are detailed in Chapter 4.

Table 2. CDE Indicators

Activity	Target	Means of verification / Dissemination channel
DIAMOND visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project to all stakeholder groups	Summary of all monitoring means
Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating data harmonisation and modelling. Fostering co-creation of assumptions, parameters, scenarios 2,000 unique users/year 40% of return visitors 	Google Analytics
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2,000 unique visitors per year 40% of return visitors 	Google Analytics account was set up when the website launched
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Project reference in 20 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	Digital monitoring, No. of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers
Social Media channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #climatediamond hashtag used 1,000 times on social media 500 followers on LinkedIn 	Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn own analytics
Commentaries, bi-monthly newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4,000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate 	Email monitoring system; Websitedownload analytics
Infographics & videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >1500 views (videos) 400 downloads (infographics) 	YouTube/Instagram statistics; No. of downloads from the website
Blog posts, press releases, and articles on news sites	At least 10 articles and press releases in the project's lifetime	Media monitoring regularly, Copies of articles shared on the website
Policy briefs, business guides	6 briefs; 2 business guides	No. of briefs/ business guides
A final EU Conference	Audience of 70-100 people	No. of attendees; minutes; photos
Scientific outreach	> 50 papers; > 20 conferences	Digital monitoring

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/>

3 Target audiences

For achieving efficient and successful CDE activities, it is crucial to have a thorough awareness of the interests and motivations of the stakeholders that are considered as target audiences for the project. As DIAMOND aims to engage with diverse audiences, the WP7 team will aim to understand the characteristics of potentially interested parties, facilitate tailored communication, and implement different engagement strategies for each audience. Table 3 shows the target audiences that have been identified at the project's start, along with preferred communication methods for each audience.

Table 3. Target audiences and preferred communication methods

Target audiences	Preferred communication methods
Scientists/Researchers/Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications and project deliverables • Scientific conferences (e.g., IAMC and ECEMP conferences) • Social media posts • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) • I²AM PARIS platform
H2020 and Horizon Europe projects, European and international modelling consortia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in EU project clustering events • Participation in modelling conferences and meetings • Mailing lists and newsletters • I²AM PARIS platform
Policymakers at all scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs and commentaries • Pitch meetings • Policy-relevant conferences and events (e.g., COP meetings, EU Sustainable Energy Week, EU Green Week) • I²AM PARIS platform
Industry decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business guides • Industry-relevant events • Social media posts • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) • I²AM PARIS platform
Civil society and NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media posts • News articles • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube)
The media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press releases • News articles

Based on the experience of the WP7 team with previous Horizon projects relating to energy and climate topics (e.g., PARIS REINFORCE², IAM COMPACT³), an initial list of stakeholders has been identified for each of the target audience categories. The list has been further enhanced through the 53 stakeholders that have been registered in the DIAMOND Stakeholder Engagement Database (Milestone 3) and have agreed on receiving news about the project. In line with the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), exchanging sensitive information about the stakeholders between partner organisations in the consortium is avoided, unless explicit consent has been provided by a stakeholder. Each partner organisation will be in charge of establishing and maintaining contact with their own stakeholders for communication purposes, under the coordination of the WP7 team.

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820846>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10105630>

4 Promotional channels and means

At the heart of the DIAMOND CDE plan is the design and implementation of promotional channels and means to reach target audiences, disseminate messages and outputs, and ensure their exploitation. The promotional channels are the routes through which the messages may find the desired destinations, including the DIAMOND project website and the I²AM PARIS platform, posts on social media, participation in conferences and others. The promotional means are the media that encapsulate the promoted message and distribute it via the proposed channels, i.e., publications, infographics, or videos.

Each combination of promotional channels and means has a particular function and level of promotion. For instance, a scientific publication contains technical details that aim to provide scientists, modellers, and researchers with a more in-depth view of the project's outcome. On the other hand, an infographic is better suited to showcase the project's concept and results to a broader audience, whereas a policy brief is expected to target policymakers.

4.1 Promotional channels

4.1.1 The DIAMOND website

The DIAMOND project's website⁴ serves as the centre of the promotional process. It is used for all three pillars of promotion and contains (or links to) every promotional material of the project. The website was developed during the first months of the project and came online in March 2023.

The website consists of the following sections and pages:

- The "About" section includes several pages on the project's description, namely its concept, objectives, work structure, and the synthesis of the scientific advisory board. This includes the "Project Consortium" page that showcases the synthesis of the consortium as well as the scientific capacity of the project partners, including links to their institutional websites.
- The "News & Events" page is used to promote all project activities, events, and significant results, while the "Communication" section of the website is dedicated to newsletters, videos, infographics, and media articles.
- The "Publications" section is used to store project deliverables, policy briefs, and business guides as well as scientific articles that acknowledge project funding.
- Lastly, the "Open science" section provides information about project synergies with other projects and modelling teams as well as presents the IAMs that will be upgraded during their project and lists their expanded capabilities. The section also includes a description and link to the I²AM PARIS modelling platform that presents detailed model documentation and results of all modelling activities of the project (see Section 4.1.2 below for more information about the platform).

The website is designed to maximise accessibility, reflecting the inclusive approach of DIAMOND. The website's colour palette is carefully curated to be in line with the DIAMOND logo and the overall visual identity. On the technical implementation, the website is developed using responsive web design, enabling access from different screen sizes and devices. Additionally, all content hosted on the website (e.g., infographics, deliverables, and

⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu>

relevant material) is provided with open access. Regarding the open-access scientific publications (and in line with open-access provisions; see Chapter 2), details such as title, authors, and journal are provided on the website, as well as links (DOIs) to the publications, directing the user to the journal-hosted version of an article and the Zenodo repository hosting relevant data.

Aiming to increase its visibility, the website was and will be continuously promoted through the other communication and dissemination channels of the project such as social media and newsletters. Moreover, several news items were already drafted to boost search engine optimisation and place the website at the top of search engine results for relevant queries. Along with the I²AM PARIS platform, the project website will stay online for at least two years after the project ends and will be key to maintaining the visibility of achievements of the project.

Several design upgrades and improvements have already taken place since the launch of the website. The website has been enriched with new content such as news items as well as reports and photos from project-related events. The purpose of these images would be to illustrate the inter- and transdisciplinary working process of DIAMOND as well as highlight the multiple dimensions of the IAMs and the practical applications of modelling results. The WP7 team will always contact individuals in photos and get their consent before publishing them online.

4.1.2 The I²AM PARIS platform

As a vessel to coordinate its climate-economy modelling activities, DIAMOND will further enhance and exploit the access to the I²AM PARIS platform. I²AM PARIS is an open-access, data exchange modelling platform developed in the context of the LC-CLA-01-2018 PARIS REINFORCE project (also coordinated by NTUA, part of ICCS). Much like DIAMOND, the platform is sustained by other H2020 (NDC ASPECTS⁵ and ENCLUDE⁶) and Horizon Europe (IAM COMPACT⁷ and TRANSIENCE⁸) projects. It is intended as a vessel for documenting IAMs, energy system models, and sectoral modelling capabilities, inputs, and outputs so that modelling exercises and their outcomes are made fully accessible and transparent to the research community, the policy world, and all other interested parties and stakeholders.

The platform will host the documentation of all modelling improvements of DIAMOND as well as the results of each modelling exercise, providing access to datasets and tailor-made visualisations, infographics, videos, policy briefs, and presentations. The platform will also function as a portal for promoting interactions among the different communities of practice and providing a common space to share inputs, definitions, and findings. In that way, the platform will facilitate data harmonisation and modelling and foster the co-creation of assumptions, parameters, and scenarios.

The platform is online but mainly contains the results and models from the PARIS REINFORCE⁹ and IAM COMPACT¹⁰ projects. In the context of DIAMOND, several new functionalities are currently underway in the platform, such as an extended suite of validation checks that can be used by project partners and other modelling teams to check their modelling results. More functionalities are planned for the 2nd year of DIAMOND and especially for the 3rd and 4th years, when more research outcomes will become available.

⁵ <https://ndc-aspects.eu/>

⁶ <https://encludeproject.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.iam-compact.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.transience.eu/>

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820846>

¹⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10105630>

4.1.3 Social media

Social media are online forums and platforms to exchange/share thoughts, opinions, knowledge, and expertise with a large audience and can be also used to host marketing, advertising efforts, and promotional campaigns. Due to the project's focus on so many diverse target audiences, it is envisaged that social media are and will be extensively used to promote messages and results to the wider public and relevant stakeholder groups (see also Chapter 3). Moreover, social media could offer a channel for comprehensible and accessible communication with target audiences as well as provide links to more in-depth dissemination resources. In terms of social media platforms, WP7 teams will continue to focus on using X (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn, and Instagram. The goal and planning for each social media channel are shown in Table 5.

Table 4. Targets and plan per social media channel

Social Media	Purpose	Plan
X	Increase project's visibility in the scientific and policymaking community, as well as in the civil society	At least one post per week on the project's progress and relevant current affairs. Posts will be more frequent later in the project when more results will be delivered. News from project partners and members of the IAM community of practice are also reposted and shared.
LinkedIn	Increase project's visibility in the scientific, policymaking, and business community	Ad hoc posts on the project's progress with an emphasis on model/result applications (scientific, business, policy), as well as reposting and sharing information from project partners and members of the IAM community of practice.
Instagram	Increase project's visibility in the wider public	Around 1-2 post(s) per month, mostly in the form of illustrations, infographics, or stories

X

X (formerly known as Twitter) is an online social networking service in which users post and interact with short messages (less than 280 characters). It is ideal for short announcements of project outcomes. Via its X account¹¹, DIAMOND is envisaged to reach a wide range of diverse audiences.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a business and employment-oriented social network, that allows individuals and organisations to promote their professional progress and outcomes. The DIAMOND project's page¹² on LinkedIn is used to target more specialised audiences within the scientific, policymaking, and business community and provide more detailed information about project outcomes.

Instagram

Instagram¹³ is a social networking app for sharing photos and videos, and it is ideal for communicating short and

¹¹ <https://twitter.com/climatediamond>

¹² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/climatediamond/>

¹³ <https://instagram.com/climatediamond?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y=>

vivid messages to wide audiences. Our goal is to achieve more active involvement of citizens in climate action based on a better understanding and demonstration of how small-scale actions contribute to the achievement of large-scale climate policy objectives including through socially innovative approaches, and a better understanding of which actions/policies are more effective. This data will help us create more nuanced decision rules for IAMs on citizens' willingness to change unsustainable behaviours and adopt climate-conscious practices. Citizen-led practices with high mitigation potential will be also disseminated in an accessible and user-friendly format to all stakeholders (e.g., in Instagram feeds or videos), encouraging them to share and repost them. We will also share all methodologies and tools for public engagement that will be developed in the project with the wider modelling community, to promote their exploitation. Stories can be used to ask followers questions to get feedback on their willingness to change.

YouTube

YouTube¹⁴ will be used for hosting and promoting DIAMOND videos, including main outputs, project events and participation in workshops.

4.1.4 News websites and blogs

The following section presents a list of high-calibre media websites that can be contacted to communicate and disseminate project outputs to a wide audience. The list is indicative and non-exhaustive and will be modified or extended whenever necessary.

EURACTIV

EURACTIV¹⁵ is an independent pan-European media network specialised in EU policymaking, covering policy processes upstream of decisions. It provides free and localised news about EU policy in twelve languages, and together with its media partners reaches 1.7 million users across Europe and the rest of the world.

The Guardian

The Guardian¹⁶ is an acknowledged British daily newspaper founded in 1821 reaching a total of 24.9 million people each month. It features a section dedicated to the environment, with subtopics on climate change, wildlife, energy, and pollution. It is envisaged that the project's outcomes can be promoted via The Guardian to a wide variety of audiences fulfilling all three pillars of promotion.

The Conversation

The Conversation¹⁷ is an independent source of news, analysis, and expert opinion, written by academics and researchers and delivered directly to the public. It is estimated that its global audience is about 14.1 million readers per month. It is envisaged that project results can be promoted via The Conversation to audiences appropriate for dissemination and exploitation.

ClimateChangePost

ClimateChangePost¹⁸ features the latest news on climate change and adaptation with a special focus on Europe.

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@climatediamond>

¹⁵ <https://www.euractiv.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/>

¹⁷ <https://theconversation.com/>

¹⁸ <https://www.climatechangepost.com/>

Many of its articles present the latest results from scientific publications and reports, making it an ideal conduit for DIAMOND to reach a wide range of its target audiences.

ClimateChangeNews.com

An international platform¹⁹ that covers climate change news, analysis, commentary, video, and podcasts focused on developments in global climate politics.

Euronews – Climate Now

For dissemination to a very wide audience, the Climate Now²⁰ programme of the Euronews channel may be a good fit for DIAMOND.

Energypost.eu

Energy Post²¹ provides an open platform to exchange and debate energy topics for policymakers, market players, analysts, and other stakeholders and could be used to reach specialised audiences for project results.

4.1.5 Magazines

Research*eu

Research*eu Results magazine²² covers topics of research interest in the EU. Through this magazine, results of DIAMOND can be communicated and disseminated to scientists, policymakers in the EU and Member States, and the general public.

4.1.6 Online collaboration and sharing platforms

Climatechangemitigation.eu

Climatechangemitigation.eu is a portal that collects and disseminates information from different EU-funded research projects on climate change mitigation. DIAMOND will use the portal²³ to promote its results to scientific and policymaking communities working on mitigation topics.

REScoop.eu

REScoop.eu²⁴ is a growing network of 1.900 European energy cooperatives and their 1.250.000 citizens who are actively participating in the energy transition. DIAMOND will use this channel to communicate and disseminate results but also recruit potential stakeholders for co-creation activities.

Energy Cities

Energy Cities²⁵ is a network of 1,000 local governments in 30 countries that establish a trustful dialogue between citizens, local leaders, and EU & national institutions to accelerate the energy transition in Europe. As with RESCOOP.eu, DIAMOND will contact Energy Cities to promote announcements related to the dissemination of

¹⁹ <https://climatechangenews.com/>

²⁰ <https://www.euronews.com/green/green-series/climate-now>

²¹ <http://energypost.eu/>

²² https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

²³ <http://climatechangemitigation.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.rescoop.eu/news-and-events>

²⁵ <https://energy-cities.eu/>

project outcomes, but also to the recruitment of participants for its activities.

Capacity4Dev

Capacity4Dev²⁶ is the European Commission's knowledge-sharing platform for development cooperation aiming to improve capacity building. The platform has over 25,000 members who share, learn, and collaborate on the fields of sustainable development. This channel is ideal for dissemination and exploitation purposes since its members are scientists, industrialists, EU staff, sustainable development professionals in the EU, policymakers at the EU and global level, as well as members of civil society.

IISD SDG Knowledge Hub

The SDG Knowledge Hub²⁷ is an online resource centre for news and commentary regarding the implementation of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including discussions on progress across all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is envisaged that our outcomes can be promoted via the IISD SDG Knowledge Hub to actors involved in sustainable development, such as policymakers, scientists, NGOs, industrialists, and civil society.

ECEEE

The European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy²⁸ is a non-profit, independent organisation dedicated to promoting energy efficiency in Europe. Since a major modelling improvement that DIAMOND will undertake relates to behavioural change towards reducing energy demand, ECEEE can be contacted to promote relevant outputs to policymakers, businesses, and NGOs related to energy efficiency.

4.1.7 Data repositories and platforms

Zenodo

Zenodo is a platform developed by CERN with the goal to provide an easy-access data repository for scientific data from all over the world and from every discipline. The DIAMOND Zenodo community²⁹ will form a central hub for providing open and unrestricted access to the project's publications and data.

GitHub

GitHub³⁰ is a platform for hosting open-source code, allowing extensive functionalities for version control and collaboration. GitHub will be used to host the code for new model functionalities that will be developed as part of DIAMOND, as well as scripts and inputs that will be used in the project's modelling exercises.

OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE³¹ is a science-related portal, the mission of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable DIAMOND, on one hand, to report more effectively and efficiently the scientific, and other, outcomes of the action and, on the other, to

²⁶ <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/>

²⁷ <http://sdg.iisd.org/>

²⁸ <https://www.eceee.org/>

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/?page=1&size=20>

³⁰ <https://github.com/>

³¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

reach a wide community of scientists, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general.

European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³² aspires to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with an open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes.

4.1.8 Partners' websites/blogs

Most consortium partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. On these websites, articles on the progress of DIAMOND and announcements on recent reports or upcoming events will be published. Partners' websites that had already published about the start of the project include the websites of ETH Zurich³³, HOLISTIC³⁴, and ICSS³⁵. Other partner websites that could be used in the future for dissemination and communication include the websites of BC3³⁶, CESAR³⁷, CICERO³⁸, CYI³⁹, EASMA⁴⁰, COMILLAS⁴¹, ISINNOVA⁴², SEURECO⁴³, UM⁴⁴, ESMIA⁴⁵, UMD⁴⁶, EPLF⁴⁷, UNIBAS⁴⁸, Imperial⁴⁹, Oxford⁵⁰, and UCL⁵¹. Project activities could also be promoted through partners' social media accounts.

4.1.9 Peer-to-peer mailing lists

Peer-to-peer (P2P) mailing lists are subscription-based email services that enable individuals interested in specific topics to communicate with each other and exchange opinions and project results. P2P lists related to DIAMOND project-related topics such as energy, IAMs, transdisciplinarity, and climate change mitigation can be powerful means to reach audiences from academia, policymaking, and business since most subscribers are actively working in sectors affected by these topics. These lists will be used to disseminate the project's progress and output (newsletters, press releases, and general announcements) and invite subscribers to participate in DIAMOND's open events and webinars. Additionally, these mailing lists will be used to follow research and novelties from

³² <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

³³ <https://ethz.ch/en.html>

³⁴ www.holisticsa.gr

³⁵ <https://www.iccs.gr/en/institute-of-communication-and-computer-systems/>

³⁶ www.bc3research.org

³⁷ <https://www.cesarecon.at/language/de/>

³⁸ www.cicero.oslo.no

³⁹ <https://www.cyi.ac.cy/>

⁴⁰ www.e4sma.com

⁴¹ <https://www.comillas.edu/en/>

⁴² <https://www.isinnova.org/about-2/history/>

⁴³ www.erasme-team.eu

⁴⁴ <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/>

⁴⁵ <https://esmia.ca/>

⁴⁶ <https://www.umd.edu/>

⁴⁷ <http://www.epfl.ch>

⁴⁸ <https://www.unibas.ch/en.html>

⁴⁹ <http://www.imperial.ac.uk>

⁵⁰ <https://www.ox.ac.uk/about>

⁵¹ <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/>

project-relevant fields.⁵²

4.1.10 External events

With the aim to effectively promote DIAMOND, partners will be encouraged to participate in events organised outside the consortium and promote preliminary and final results, both during and after the end of the project. This includes events organised by the European Commission as well as international conferences and workshop fields related to the project's scope. All partners will participate in the identification of relevant events.

Scientific conferences

DIAMOND partners will participate in scientific conferences to disseminate the project results to the scientific community. Additionally, conferences will be used to monitor relevant research in fields related to energy citizenship and other relevant topics. The following conferences have been assessed as relevant to the project:

- European Climate + Energy Modelling Platform (ECEMP)⁵³
- Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC)⁵⁴
- International Energy Workshop⁵⁵
- Energy Modeling Forum⁵⁶
- International Transdisciplinary Conference⁵⁷
- Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES) conference⁵⁸

Policy conferences

Along the duration of DIAMOND from December 2022 to November 2026, four sessions of the UNFCCC's Conference of the Parties (COP) had and will take place. These conferences offer great opportunities to reach out to policymakers, NGOs, industrialists, scientists, and other audiences and promote the project. In terms of European-specific conferences, the European Sustainable Development Week⁵⁹ and the European Sustainable Energy Week⁶⁰ will be policy-relevant fora for presenting the project's results.

Workshops and other events and media

A series of workshops with key stakeholder groups will take place in the context of the modelling work, to inform our activities and outcomes and ensure their relevance. These workshops will also serve as dissemination fora, where knowledge and information generated will be shared and discussed. A final EU conference will take place to inform policy, other stakeholders, and the broader modelling research community on the project's IAM improvements and advanced, sustainable mitigation pathways. Building on lessons learnt from the COVID-19 pandemic, most workshops in the context of the co-design nature of the DIAMOND project will be organised in a

⁵² <https://enb.iisd.org/email/>

⁵³ <https://www.ecemf.eu/ecemp/european-climate-and-energy-modelling-platform/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/annual-meetings/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.internationalenergyworkshop.org>

⁵⁶ <https://emf.stanford.edu>

⁵⁷ <https://akademien-schweiz.ch/en/current/events/itd-conference-2021/>

⁵⁸ <https://www.sdewes.org/>

⁵⁹ <https://esdw.eu>

⁶⁰ https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en

digital format. This will help to avoid the environmental and economic impact of travelling, while also circumventing potential travel restrictions due to pandemic-related restrictions, as well as reducing the time investment from the participants.

4.1.11 Synergies

Synergies with relevant projects can increase the outreach potential of the project's outputs and raise awareness among a broad spectrum of stakeholders. DIAMOND will contact projects of interest and co-organise synergetic activities such as participating in each other's events and cross-disseminating information and outputs through social media and project websites. DIAMOND has already established connections with the WorldTrans⁶¹ sister project, where the project coordinator (Dr Cecilie Mauritzen) of WorldTrans has been invited to the DIAMOND Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and vice versa. Additionally, the NTUA section of ICCS is coordinating the IAM COMPACT project which is focusing on the same domain of climate change mitigation as DIAMOND and will run in parallel, offering many options for synergies between the projects. The DIAMOND website already contains a section on such synergistic activities⁶².

In parallel with co-creation activities with other research projects, DIAMOND aims to enhance communities of practice for climate-economy modelling. We will establish active channels for two-way communication and synergies with existing modelling consortia and communities such as IAMC⁶³, GCAM Community, and IEA-ETSAP⁶⁴. We will go beyond the usual synergies among such communities by aiming to encourage an open-source development process for the project's improved IAMs with the collaboration of external modellers.

4.2 Branding and promotional materials

Several types of promotional materials are envisaged to promote the DIAMOND project scope, objectives, and results in different stages of the project. All promotional materials have a consistent and distinctive visual identity and have been created within the first six months of the project⁶⁵.

4.2.1 Visual identity and communication package

Visual identity and logo

It is important to have a simple but distinctive and appealing visual identity (D7.1) early on in the project that should convey the message of what the project is about. The logo was custom-made for DIAMOND and its blue and yellow hues were chosen intentionally. Blue is the most universally appealing colour on the spectrum because of its non-polarising traits; it is usually used in corporate logos related to software, finance, and technology as it creates a sense of security while showing professionalism. Yellow shows optimism and enlightenment but also caution, while brands that are seeking to draw in consumers with youthful energy often utilise this colour. In addition, the project's relation with the six IAMs also be depicted on the logo, as the shapes are six in number, and all together create a diamond of models.

⁶¹ <https://sites.google.com/met.no/worldtrans/home>

⁶² <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

⁶³ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/>

⁶⁴ <https://iea-etsap.org/>

⁶⁵ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/visual-identity/>

(especially among non-experts).

4.2.2 Promotional materials

Blog posts, articles, and press releases

Articles on climate action and energy strategies in leading media websites and blogs will be disseminated via the promotional channels identified in Section 4.1. Additionally, press releases will be developed by the WP7 team, disseminated through the website's newsletter, and promoted to relevant media. All partners will support this process by suggesting media contacts at the national level and extending the list of interesting media targets. At least 10 articles and press releases are expected to be published in the project's course.

Scientific publications

Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and building scientific credibility for the project's work. Scientific articles will be published in open-access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals. Partners will also be encouraged and assisted in publishing their results in working paper series. These activities will ensure that the project and its results will be made known to the public at large. Journals also offering open peer review, such as Open Research Europe, will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated project OpenAIRE/Zenodo community, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability. Moreover, the WP7 team will use its social media channels to promote the articles. A special issue is also envisioned using the consortium partners' connections to respective journal editors to further support the scientific dissemination and exploitation of the project's results.

DIAMOND newsletter

The newsletter's goal is to create awareness and involve stakeholders in progress. A regular electronic newsletter is issued providing information on the project development and events every 2-3 months. The newsletter will incorporate inputs from all partners on the progress and key outcomes of the project. Its key aim is to create awareness about the ongoing work of the action and involve stakeholders in progress. In compliance with the GDPR, a person will be included on the newsletter mailing list only if one is informed and explicit consent has been given, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consent will be provided either by filling out an online subscription form or by direct email in case of personal contacts.

Press releases at partners' institutions

DIAMOND provides regularly the communication departments of all consortium partners with content to be processed for the partners' newsletters, websites, and other media channels.

5 Implemented activities as of May 2024

During the first 18 months of the project, several CDE activities have been implemented. Nevertheless, dissemination efforts are expected to intensify during the next years when most deliverables and scientific products of DIAMOND will be available. As of May 2024, eleven out of the 50 project deliverables have been finalised, with most of them used to create the groundwork for DIAMOND scientific work in the coming years. For now, the WP7 team aimed to establish a strong presence on social media, creating weekly posts derived from the project’s concept and methodology. Figure 2 shows the project’s CDE tracker, including a selection of implemented activities. The tracker is used to monitor and document events and media activities of the project; it is available online⁷⁰ and is frequently updated. The following sections show implemented activities in more detail.

Date	Responsible partner	Type of media activity (select from drop-down list)	Title media activity / Description	Country / Medium	N° of ppl reached	Dissemination level (local, regional, national, European...)									
						Scientific community	Industry	Civil society	General public	Policy makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other (who)	
12/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, As competitive this duo (#Serbia and...)	N/a	135 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
		Social Media	Twitter Post, Day 1 of the @climatediamond kick-off meeting! This project will update, upgrade and fully open 6 IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution and geographic granularity. #climatediamond	N/a	410 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
15/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	451 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
15/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, Day 2 of @climatediamond kick-off meeting. Today, we discussed about the challenges, opportunities, and near-term objectives concerning our project. Our partners presented their 6 IAMs and the expanding model capabilities. Stay tuned as there are more to come! #climatediamond	N/a	2,013 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
16/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	710 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
16/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, In 2023, @climatediamond will kickstart its journey to update, upgrade & open 6 major #IAMs! We will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process, co-create research questions and establish vibrant communities of practice. Stay tuned!	N/a	267 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
3/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	326 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
3/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, Introducing #climatediamond Consortium members: ICCS is @climatediamond's coordinator, will lead open science activities & model improvement & use (GCAM, PROMETHEUS, CLEWs). ICCS areas of expertise are the coordination of large modelling consortia; IAMs; co-creation & risk/uncertainty	N/a	348 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
11/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	427 x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global

Figure 2. Screenshot of project tracker for CDE monitoring

5.1 Progress towards CDE indicators

Table 5. Progress towards CDE Indicators by Month 18

Activity	Target	Progress by Month 18
DIAMOND visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project to all stakeholder groups	Finished developing the visual identity of the project and the basic communication package

⁷⁰ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVxm8JBMrAVg7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMIhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

		(e.g., leaflets, poster, project presentation) ⁷¹
Enhanced I ² AM PARIS platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating data harmonisation and modelling. Fostering co-creation of assumptions, parameters, scenarios 2,000 unique users/year 40% of return visitors 	Platform enhancements are currently underway, while most of them will be developed in the 2 nd half of the project
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2,000 unique visitors per year 40% of return visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2031 unique visitors (May 2023 to May 2024) 14% return visitors
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Project reference in 20 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	9 joint publications with other projects ⁷² and 1 joint presentation
Social Media channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #climatediamond hashtag used 1,000 times on social media 500 followers on LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 612 uses of the hashtag or project handle (including reposts) 654 followers on X 555 followers on LinkedIn 426 followers on Instagram
Commentaries, bi-monthly newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4,000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate 	648 recipients, 39% opening rate
Infographics & videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >1500 views (videos) 400 downloads (infographics) 	No video or infographic yet
Blog posts, press releases, and articles on news sites	At least 10 articles and press releases in the project's lifetime	No media article yet
Policy briefs, business guides	6 briefs; 2 business guides	No briefs or guides yet
A final EU Conference	Audience of 70-100 people	Will be organised towards the end of the project
Scientific outreach	> 50 papers; > 20 conferences	11 papers acknowledging DIAMOND ⁷³ ; 13 conference presentations, posters, and sessions chaired (see Section 5.6)

5.2 Website

The DIAMOND project website is online since March 2023 and provides a comprehensive information portal about the project. It is also used as an archive of all activities of the project, including the first public deliverables, newsletter, and infographics. Currently, searching for “climate diamond” shows the website at the top of Google search results, while traffic to the website has been mainly driven through the social media accounts of the project. In total, the website had 2031 unique visitors within the last 12 months, achieving the target of 2000 visitors per year. However, returning visitors over the same period are only 14%, which is lower than the target of 40% that was set. Nevertheless, this number is expected to increase as more project products are developed and promoted on the website.

⁷¹ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/visual-identity/>

⁷² <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

⁷³ <https://climate-diamond.eu/publications/scientific-publications/>

5.3 Social Media

The online presence of DIAMOND has been already established on X, LinkedIn, and Instagram. Specifically, an official DIAMOND account⁷⁴ has been created on Twitter and has attracted 654 followers till now. Moreover, a LinkedIn organisation webpage⁷⁵ has been created to disseminate our actions and results to more business-oriented audiences and gained 555 users, achieving the KPI of 500 users. An Instagram account⁷⁶ has been also created and is used to disseminate visual material and infographics, featuring until now 426 followers. An impression of the items posted until now on Twitter and LinkedIn is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A selection of project posts in social media

5.4 Articles on other websites

Six partners have already referenced DIAMOND on their project websites (see Figure 4) and have already interacted with the project on social media. Additionally, the website of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium has also referenced the project⁷⁷. Other websites are expected to acknowledge the project such as the climatechangemitigation.eu portal. All references from other websites to DIAMOND are shown on the CDE tracker⁷⁸.

⁷⁴ <https://twitter.com/climatediamond>

⁷⁵ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/climatediamond/>

⁷⁶ <https://www.instagram.com/climatediamond/?next=%2F>

⁷⁷ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/news-from-the-community/news-f-the-community/diamond-project/>

⁷⁸ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVm8JBMrAVg7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMIhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

Figure 4. References of DIAMOND on other websites

5.5 Scientific publications

Despite that most research outputs of the project will be released later in its duration, 11 journal articles have been already published acknowledging DIAMOND. All articles were published using the Gold Open Access option and are thus directly and freely accessible to the public.

Overall, the following published articles have acknowledged DIAMOND:

1. Moreno, J., Campagnolo, L., Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Perdana, S., Van de Ven, D.-J., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Gargiulo, M., Herbst, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Neuner, F., Le Mouél, P., & Vielle, M. (2024). The impacts of decarbonization pathways on Sustainable Development Goals in the European Union. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 1–14.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01309-7>

2. McGookin, C., Süsser, D., Xexakis, G., Trutnevyte, E., McDowall, W., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Few, S., Andersen, P. D., Demski, C., Fortes, P., Simoes, S. G., Bishop, C., Rogan, F., & Ó Gallachóir, B. (2024). Advancing participatory energy systems modelling. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 52, 101319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101319>
3. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2024). Three different directions in which the European Union could replace Russian natural gas. *Energy*, 130254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130254>
4. Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, D.-J. van de Ven, Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU's path to net zero. *Joule*, 7(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.11.002>
5. Perdana, S., Vielle, M., & Oliveira, T. D. (2024). The EU carbon border adjustment mechanism: Implications on Brazilian energy intensive industries. *Climate Policy*, 24(2), 260–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2277405>
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5.6 Events

DIAMOND project has organised a side event at the UNFCCC's 28th Conference of the Parties (COP 28) in Dubai. The event was organised in the Greek Pavillion at COP28 and was moderated by the DIAMOND consortium member Prof. Ryna Yiyun Cui, (*University of Maryland, US*). The agenda included the following interventions, also

by members of the DIAMOND consortium:

- “Paving the way to net zero in the EU: key technologies, strategic decisions, and a roadmap” Speaker: Haris Doukas, *Professor at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), President of the Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage (ELLET) Energy Council, Mayor of the Municipality of Athens, Greece.*
- “Defining ‘Abated Fossil Fuels’ and identifying their role in the EU’s long-term ambition” Speaker: Alaa Al Khourdajie, *Research Fellow at the Department of Chemical Engineering of Imperial College London (Imperial)*
- “The role of gas in the EU’s net-zero trajectory: thinking in the context of the energy crisis” Speaker: Steve Pye, *Assoc. Professor at the UCL Energy Institute (University College London)*

Figure 5. Flyer from the side-event organised by DIAMOND at COP28

In terms of scientific conferences, DIAMOND partners participated in three major events of the climate and climate-economy modelling community, namely the EGU2024, IAMC 2023, and ECEMP 2023. The following presentations and posters have acknowledged DIAMOND:

1. Sampedro, J., Khan, Z., Mittal, S., Kikstra, J. (2024). Incorporating equity, gender, health and other co-benefits into NEXUS and IAM research, EGU General Assembly 2024 [ITS3.27/ERE6.6 session]
2. Herbig, V., Briers, S., and Vienni-Baptista, B. (2024). From Stakeholder Engagement to Inclusivity: Advancing Participatory Modeling for Net-Zero Sustainable Development, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-9297, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-9297>, 2024. [presentation]
3. García-Muros, X., Alonso-Epelde, E., González-Eguino, M., and Rodríguez-Zúñiga, A. (2024). Can energy and environmental taxation be progressive in the EU?, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-10785, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-10785>, 2024. [presentation]
4. Van de Ven, D.-J. and Sampedro, J. (2024). Passenger transport decarbonisation under different equity

- considerations, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-19615, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19615>, 2024. [poster]
5. Frilingou, N., van de Ven, D.-J., Mittal, S., Karamaneas, A., Nikolakakis, T., Gardumi, F., Koasidis, K., and Nikas, A. (2024). How do interest rates affect decarbonisation pathways? A stakeholder-driven multi-model analysis., EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-17148, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17148>, 2024. [poster]
 6. Alonso-Epelde, E., Rodés, C., and Moyano-Reina, M. (2024). MEDUSA – Modelling Equity and DistribUtional impacts for Socioeconomic Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-5065>, 2024. [poster]
 7. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2023). Three corner options for replacing Russian gas imports in Europe: a multi-model analysis. IAMC 2023. [presentation]
 8. van de Ven, D.-J., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzo, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, , Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU's path to net zero. IAMC 2023. [presentation]
 9. Boitier, B. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of the EU's path to net zero: aligning near-term action with long-term visions. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]
 10. Frilingou, N. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of European strategies to eliminate Russian gas imports. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]
 11. Vielle M. and Perdana. S. (2023). Mapping the transition: Industrial European regions at risk within the fit for 55. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]
 12. Xexakis G. (2023). Dependency & Energy Security. ECEMP 2023. [session chair]

Additionally, 10 internal events have been already organised by the DIAMOND team, including general meetings and meetings between the modelling teams of the project (see Figure 6 for screenshots from these meetings). Details about the most major meetings can be found on the website⁷⁹ while the full list of events can be found on the dissemination tracker⁸⁰. In the coming years, DIAMOND partners are expected to organise and participate in even more events, helping to build communities of practice in climate modelling and to promote project results.

⁷⁹ <https://climate-diamond.eu/news-events/>

⁸⁰ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVn8JBMrAVg7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMlhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

Figure 6. Photos from events that DIAMOND has participated in as of May 2024

5.7 Synergies

Several synergies have already been established between DIAMOND and relevant European projects⁸¹. Nine out of the 11 journal publications that are currently acknowledging DIAMOND have been published as a synergy with other projects, most notably, the Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT and Horizon 2020 PARIS REINFORCE projects. Additionally, on 17 April 2024, DIAMOND co-organised along with its sister project WorldTrans a presentation on the design of an interactive policy platform for climate change mitigation and adaptation. The meeting also included a discussion on further synergies between WorldTrans and DIAMOND (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Example of synergies between WorldTrans and DIAMOND (discussed during April 2024)

Lastly, DIAMOND participates in the MAIA Multiply programme, organised by the Horizon Europe MAIA project⁸² which serves as an aggregator and amplifier of the results of Horizon projects on climate topics (see Figure 8 for

⁸¹ <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

⁸² <https://maia-project.eu>

an example). MAIA also provides networking opportunities and CDE advice to participating projects, further increasing the impact of DIAMOND to its target audience.

Figure 8. The MAIA multiply program that DIAMOND is participating in

5.8 Newsletters and press releases

DIAMOND has released five newsletters and three press releases as of May 2024. The newsletters have mostly aggregated news about the project as they were published on the website⁸³. In contrast, press releases have mostly focused on key activities of the project, for instance, the publication of a flagship journal article on the EU’s path to net zero and the participation of DIAMOND in UNFCCC’s COP28. Figure 9 shows a screenshot of the first newsletter, while copies of all newsletters are available on the project’s website⁸⁴.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the project’s first newsletter

5.9 Infographics

Some first infographics have been developed catching the pulse of the FIFA World Cup 2022 and building up audience for project social media accounts. We produced several infographics showcasing the greenhouse gas

⁸³ <https://climate-diamond.eu/news-events/>

⁸⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/newsletters-press-releases/>

emissions of countries participating in the World Cup. Figure 10 shows an example while all infographics are available on the project website⁸⁵. More infographics will be developed when more project materials become available.

Figure 10. Infographics for FIFA World Cup 2022

⁸⁵ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/infographics/>

6 Next steps

During the first 18 months of DIAMOND, the main goal of its CDE plan was to establish the project's visual identity and website, gain a strong following in social media, and develop some first communication content, including posts on events and publications acknowledging the project. This goal is successful as shown by the current size of the project audience on LinkedIn (555 followers, KPI was 500 followers), Instagram (426 followers), and X (654 followers) and the 2,031 unique website visitors within the last 12 months (KPI was 2,000 visitors). Nevertheless, dissemination would need to ramp up during the next 2.5 project years in order to reach the intended CDE performance, for instance, reaching the target of 40% returning visitors from the current 14%. Additionally, DIAMOND has built its networks with significant modelling consortia (e.g., IAMC, ECEMP, and GCAM communities) and relevant projects (e.g., IAM COMPACT, PARIS REINFORCE, MAIA), leading to nine publications developed as synergies between DIAMOND and these projects. It is expected that these collaborations will amplify in the coming years as more scientific outputs and, thus, more opportunities for synergies will become available.

Apart from having more content to disseminate, the WP7 team aims to take the following actions to further improve the CDE performance of the project:

Website: More content will be included in the coming months such as deliverables, publications, videos, and infographics.

Social media: The WP7 team will continue to post at least once a week on social media. This dissemination is expected to intensify as research outcomes of the project become available. The WP7 team will also become more active on Instagram by developing and posting visual material and infographics that promote the project and its outcomes.

Media: Along with efforts to intensify social media presence, the WP7 team will produce at least 10 articles for media outlets and blogs. The articles will be based on the research outputs of the project and will aim to both increase awareness about DIAMOND and its goals and also contribute to attracting audiences beyond academia and research.

Publications: DIAMOND has already 11 scientific publications and aims to significantly increase them by submitting more research work to high-profile conferences and journals within the coming months and years.

Newsletter: Conditional to available project content, 4-6 newsletters are expected to be sent per year during the project's lifetime. Newsletter subscribers will be also increased by promoting the newsletter to our social media, partners' social media and other interested parties.

Infographics: As project results become available, new infographics will be prepared.

7 References

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